

Promoting early arithmetical skills by using part-whole thinking as a way to guide joint learning for students of all abilities

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This paper presents preliminary findings of the large-scale project Counting with all children from the very beginning, (Mit allen Kindern von Anfang an rechnen) a project that has the aim of developing and testing joint teaching-learning situations in primary schools, based on part-whole thinking ('Teile-Ganzes-Denken') from children's first maths lessons. Using design research, five mainstream teachers volunteered to participate in the Beta-cycle over a ten-week period in First Grade. Data analysis revealed that not all the teachers managed to define coherent aims for their students' mathematical learning, especially in the instances of children who have poor mathematical skills and of children with special educational needs (SEN).

Preliminary remarks

International organisations such as UNICEF, UNESCO or the European Union, define 'the right to education' as a common ideal regarding inclusion of all people. With the passage of time, the Austrian education system, like that of many other countries, has made great progress as far as the issue of inclusion is concerned. Since 1885, there have been special educational classes for children with learning difficulties, initially called 'auxiliary classes' and subsequently changed in 1956 to 'special schools'. A wide range of special schools were established as the proper place for children and young people with disabilities. The number of different special schools reached a peak in the 1980s with 10 different types available. Austrians' first attempts at integrative education in mainstream primary schools were in the 1980s (Buchner & Proyer, 2020). With the ratification of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in 2008, Austria set out on a path towards an inclusive education system. Even today, Austria, like many other countries in the world, still focuses on a so-called two-track approach: Parents are free to decide whether to send their child to a special school or a mainstream school. In 2018-19, of the 578,417 school-age children approximately 5% (29,000) had SEN. 63% of the children with SEN were included in mainstream schools, while 37% attended a special school (Statistik Austria, 2019). Currently the main focus of inclusive education is to promote the quality of teaching-learning situations (Florian, 2008). There seems to be uncertainty, and not only in German-speaking countries, about how to teach inclusively and how to create inclusive teaching-learning situations, mainly in early

Please cite as: Gander, C. (2021). Promoting early arithmetical skills by using part-whole thinking as a way to guide joint learning for students of all abilities. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 159–162). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5387825>

arithmetical education (Korff, 2016). Thus, this project seeks to design teaching-learning situations for First Grade based on part-whole thinking, in order to support teachers in their challenging task.

The TIGER concept of part-whole thinking

It seems to be accepted in the relevant German literature that at the end of First Grade children should learn that numbers (up to 20) are composed of other numbers. It might be helpful if teachers first focus on the consolidation of part-whole thinking and then, based merely on that, initiate children's understanding of addition and subtraction (see also, for example, Gaidoschik, 2019). These goals seem to be the norm in international mathematics education also, with for example 'Number framework' (New Zealand Ministry of Education, NZME, 2008) or 'Mathematics programme of study' (UK Department of Education, 2013). Part-whole thinking is incorporated as early as possible in the school programme in these guidelines for teachers' actions. The TIGER (Teile im Ganzen Erkennen und damit Rechnen) concept, developed by Gaidoschik (2017), focuses on solid number concepts in early arithmetical teaching. The concept consists of three fundamental aspects. Firstly, counting with an understanding of numbers. This includes children learning how to work out the 'counting principles' of Gelman and Gallistel (1987). Secondly, comparing quantities and numbers. On the basis of one-to-one matching up, children should learn and/or consolidate that no counting is needed for pairing the items or for number comparison such as identifying that there is one more left over. The third area is that of subitizing or perceptual subitizing without counting (see also, for example, Clements & Sarama, 2009). Teachers should work with students in all fields more or less concurrently.

The research project, research method and research question

The 13 teaching-learning situations of the current research project are based on the ideas of the TIGER concept, with a balance between individual and mutual learning. To be able to examine the effectiveness of the learning environments, collective case studies in the framework of design-based research (Euler, 2014) have been conducted. Within the framework of an Alpha-cycle, conducted in school year 2019-2020 with 45 First Grade students in two Tyrolean mainstream classes, video-recorded conclusions were drawn for the implementation, analysis and further development of the teaching-learning situations. The results were processed in an additional cycle. The Beta-cycle, which is relevant for data analysis, was carried out in five Tyrolean primary school classes in school year 2020-2021 with 95 pupils. To generate insights into students learning, each lesson was video recorded. Thus, in this paper, I write about six and seven-year-old children of the Beta-cycle over a 10-week period in First Grade in inclusive mainstream classes in Austria. The questions guiding the study are: Can teaching-learning situations based on part-whole thinking be designed to foster learning processes in early arithmetical teaching of all students in primary school? How should such teaching-learning situations be designed? A combination of 'Abstraction

in Context' (Dreyfus & Kidron, 2014) and 'Assessment of Teaching-Learning-Situations in Mathematics of the Early Grades' (Steinweg, 2010) is used for data analysis. AiC is a theoretical framework to analyze students' processes of constructing abstract mathematical knowledge. There are three epistemic actions: Recognizing (R), Building-with (B) and Constructing (C), hence the RBC-model. Steinweg's idea of dimensions focuses on the teachers' possibilities for action. The combination of both approaches gives indications for further development of teaching-learning situations.

Interim results

The following brief sequence of the teaching-learning situation Throwing Tiles focuses on six-year-old girls Anna and Rosa. They take turns throwing the 10 reversible tiles, which have a red side and a blue side. Then together they have to match one red with one blue tile, using one-to-one matching without counting (AiC - Recognizing). They create two rows to identify who has more tiles, and how many more there are of one colour than the other. Anna has six blue tiles, Rosa four red tiles. The teacher joins in:

- Teacher: Great! Both of you have already thrown tiles and matched them in two rows. Each blue tile in the top row has a red tile in the bottom row. Rosa, how many tiles do you have less than Anna?
- Rosa: I'd better count them again. *(Rosa takes her red tiles and starts again).*
- Teacher: How many tiles do you have, Rosa? Did you have to count them again?
- Rosa: I have four. *(Rosa is uncertain again).*
- Teacher: *(The teacher takes the blue tiles and arranges them in a row).* Can you match a red one of yours with each blue tile?
- Rosa: Yes. *(Rosa puts a red tile on each blue tile in a second row).*
- Teacher: Great. How many tiles more does Anna have than you? *(The teacher points to both rows with her index finger).*
- Rosa: Six? *(Rosa is unsure how to answer).*

Analyzing the transcript using AiC indicates that the ideal of learning processes is not achieved by all children. Regarding Steinweg's idea of dimensions, not all teachers were able to foster children's competence in one-to-one matching, as seen in Rosa's lack of understanding of the one-to-one matching up process. Particular attention should be paid to the mathematical thinking of underachieving children and to children with SEN, as in the case of Rosa mentioned above. In this sequence, the teacher did not realize that Rosa requires a solid understanding for one-to-one matching up (AiC - Recognizing) as a basis for further arithmetical strategies (AiC - Building with and Constructing). No further improvements need to be made to the teaching-learning situation Throwing Tiles. It is important to boost teachers' didactical knowledge and their knowledge of possibilities in the early arithmetical education of all children. In Austria, one third of children with SEN are integrated into mainstream primary school classes, but we can presume that their mathematical competence is not being continuously fostered, and neither are the abilities of children with poor

mathematical skills. Most authors, at least in the relevant German mathematics education literature, seem to agree that these children do not need completely different concepts, but instead need targeted support from highly qualified class teachers and teaching assistants.

References

- Buchner, T. & Proyer, M. (2019). From special to inclusive education policies in Austria – developments and implications for schools and teacher education. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(1), 83-94. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2019.1691992>
- Clements, D. H. & Sarama, J. (2009). *Learning and Teaching Early Math: The Learning Trajectories Approach*. Routledge.
- Dreyfus, T., & Kidron, I. (2014). Introduction to abstraction in context (AiC). In A. Bikner-Ahsbals & S. Prediger (Eds.), *Networking of Theories as a Research Practice in Mathematics Education* (pp. 85-96). Springer.
- Euler, D. (2014). Design Research – a paradigm under development. In D. Euler (Ed.), *Design-Based Research* (pp. 15-41). Steiner.
- Florian, L. (2008). INCLUSION: Special or inclusive education: future trends. *British Journal of Special Education*, 35(4), 202-208. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8578.2008.00402.x>
- Gaidoschik, M. (2019). Didactics as a source and remedy of mathematics learning difficulties. In A. Fritz, V. Haase, & P. Räsänen (Eds.), *The International Handbook of Math Learning Difficulties: From the Lab to the Classroom* (pp. 73-89). Springer.
- Gelman, R. & Gallistel, C.R. (1987). *The Child's Understanding of Number*. Harvard University Press.
- Korff, N. (2016). *Inklusiver Mathematikunterricht in der Primarstufe: Erfahrungen, Perspektiven und Herausforderungen* (3. Aufl.). Schneider Hohengehren.
- New Zealand Ministry of Education (2008). *Getting Started*. Crown.
- UK Department of Education (2013). *Mathematics programme of study: key stages 1 and 2*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-curriculum-in-england-mathematics-programmes-of-study>
- Statistik Austria (2018/19). *Schülerinnen und Schüler mit sonderpädagogischem Förderbedarf*. Retrieved from https://www.statistik.at/web_de/statistiken/menschen_und_gesellschaft/bildung/schulen/schulbesuch/029658.html
- Steinweg, A.S. (2010). Einschätzung der Qualität von Lehr-Lernsituationen im mathematischen Anfangsunterricht – ein Vorschlag. *Journal für Mathematik-Didaktik*, 32(1), 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13138-010-0022-y>